

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN DESCRIPTION

DATA MINING

Data mining is looking for hidden, valid, and potentially useful patterns in huge data sets. Data Mining is all about discovering unsuspected/ previously unknown relationships amongst the data. It is a multi-disciplinary skill that uses machine learning, statistics, AI and database technology.

Data mining is also called as Knowledge discovery, Knowledge extraction, data/pattern analysis, information harvesting, etc.

Data mining is a big area of data sciences, which aims to discover patterns and features in data, often large data sets. It includes regression, classification, clustering, detection of anomaly, and others. It also includes preprocessing, validation, summarization, and ultimately the making sense of the data sets.

Data Mining Techniques

1. Classification:

This analysis is used to retrieve important and relevant information about data, and metadata. This data mining method helps to classify data in different classes.

2. Clustering:

Clustering analysis is a data mining technique to identify data that are like each other. This process helps to understand the differences and similarities between the data.

3. Regression:

Regression analysis is the data mining method of identifying and analyzing the relationship between variables. It is used to identify the likelihood of a specific variable, given the presence of other variables.

4. Association Rules:

This data mining technique helps to find the association between two or more Items. It discovers a hidden pattern in the data set.

5. Outer detection:

This type of data mining technique refers to observation of data items in the dataset which do not match an expected pattern or expected behavior. This technique can be used in a variety of domains, such as intrusion, detection, fraud or fault detection, etc. Outer detection is also called Outlier Analysis or Outlier mining.

6. Sequential Patterns:

This data mining technique helps to discover or identify similar patterns or trends in transaction data for certain period.

7. Prediction:

Prediction has used a combination of the other data mining techniques like trends, sequential patterns, clustering, classification, etc. It analyzes past events or instances in a right sequence for predicting a future event.

Benefits of Data Mining:

- Data mining technique helps companies to get knowledge-based information.
- Data mining helps organizations to make the profitable adjustments in operation and production.
- The data mining is a cost-effective and efficient solution compared to other statistical data applications.
- Data mining helps with the decision-making process.

- Facilitates automated prediction of trends and behaviors as well as automated discovery of hidden patterns.
- It can be implemented in new systems as well as existing platforms
- It is the speedy process which makes it easy for the users to analyze huge amount of data in less time.

MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning is an application of artificial intelligence (AI) that provides systems the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of computer programs that can access data and use it learn for themselves. The process of learning begins with observations or data, such as examples, direct experience, or instruction, in order to look for patterns in data and make better decisions in the future based on the examples that we provide. The primary aim is to allow the computers learn automatically without human intervention or assistance and adjust actions accordingly.

Machine Learning Methods

Machine learning algorithms are often categorized as supervised or unsupervised.

Supervised machine learning algorithms can apply what has been learned in the past to new data using labeled examples to predict future events. Starting from the analysis of a known training dataset, the learning algorithm produces an inferred function to make predictions about the output values. The system is able to provide targets for any new input after sufficient training. The learning algorithm can also compare its output with the correct, intended output and find errors in order to modify the model accordingly.

In contrast, **unsupervised machine learning algorithms** are used when the information used to train is neither classified nor labeled. Unsupervised learning studies how systems can infer a function to describe a hidden structure from unlabeled data. The system doesn't figure out the right output, but it explores the data and can draw inferences from datasets to describe hidden structures from unlabeled data.

Semi-supervised machine learning algorithms fall somewhere in between supervised and unsupervised learning, since they use both labeled and unlabeled data for training – typically a small amount of labeled data and a large amount of unlabeled data. The systems that use this method are able to considerably improve learning accuracy. Usually, semi-supervised learning is chosen when the acquired labeled data requires skilled and relevant resources in order to train it / learn from it. Otherwise, acquiring unlabeled data generally doesn't require additional resources.

Reinforcement machine learning algorithms is a learning method that interacts with its environment by producing actions and discovers errors or rewards. Trial and error search and delayed reward are the most relevant characteristics of reinforcement learning. This method allows machines and software agents to automatically determine the ideal behavior within a specific context in order to maximize its performance. Simple reward feedback is required for the agent to learn which action is best; this is known as the reinforcement signal.

Applications of Machine Learning

1. Virtual Personal Assistants
2. Predictions while Commuting
3. Social Media Services
4. Email Spam and Malware Filtering
5. Online Fraud Detection

1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

The biometric facial recognition software with banking software is more conventional methods. In fact, using passwords comes with a rather serious caveat. People create passwords based on what they know. So it is easy for a hacker to employ a number of tactics to crack the password. Another major flaw is that people can have too many passwords eg. for social media accounts, emails, and e-wallets as well. Also, creating a complex password can make it easier to forget and when a banking customer requests for a temporary code via email to reset it, then a hacker can intercept the inbox. Using facial recognition means that the banking customer has only one face which can allow them access to all their bank accounts.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Facial recognition is one of numerous ways banks can decrease friction in their customers' experience and increase efficiency and accessibility. This project make Identity Verification and Account Withdrawals Allowing customers to make withdrawals from their bank accounts. The biometric facial-recognition software helps minimize fraud where online hackers unlawfully use passwords and other data to steal from banking institutions. The software verifies a person's identity before processing any transaction. Our goal is to provide an extremely frictionless, personalized experience with a focus on security.

In addition to this, we have proposed a next level of security by providing the pin that is generated through an E-mail instantaneously once recognition of the face has been completed successfully. If the face features that has been recognized does not match with the registered face of the banking customers, then the transaction process cannot be proceeded further since the recognized face is unauthorized.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: Transaction Authorization from Know Your Customer (KYC) Information in Online Banking

Authors: Prakash Chandra Mondal, Rupam Deb and Mohammad Nurul Huda

Online banking is getting popularity due to location independence, 24/7 services and responsiveness. Financial services through the internet are running under various threats like phishing, pharming (cyber attack intended to redirect a website's traffic to another fake site), malware, Man-In-The-Middle (MITM) attack and the evolving sophistication of compromise techniques. One time password (OTP) in online banking system alleviate the risk and make it secure. In various methods of OTP and Mobile Transaction Authentication Number (mTAN), device can be lost or stolen, delivery in delay, etc. Compliance with Anti-Money Laundering (AML), Know Your Customer (KYC) and sanctions requirements continues to be a key focus area for financial institution (FI) management, and firms must ensure they are following appropriate compliance procedures to meet the increasing regulatory demands [1, 2]. Addressing existing limitation of OTP, this paper proposes Challenge Question (CQ) from dynamic KYC database for transaction authorization before committing any financial transaction from online banking application. Analysis and simulation results show that the proposed method provides equal control as existing OTP/mTAN.

Paper 2: A Robust and secure authentication mechanism in online banking

Authors: Hridya Venugopal, N Viswanath

Online banking is on the up each day with a persistent rise in the number of people using this novel service to carry out their financial transactions. This amplified interest in the use of online banking has consequently raised the concerns over the security. This has raised the need to protect online banking in to guard these transactions as well as establishing secure mechanisms for information exchange that prevent fraud and safeguard the personal data. With the internet now popular among all age groups, online banking has become a necessity. Security mechanisms are, therefore a must for the proper functioning of online banking. In addition to this, all the users are required to manage multiple passwords and devices. Security which are provided by the extensively used systems namely knowledge-based security and token-based security can be easily breached when one reveals his password and his cards are stolen. In order to overcome this, biometrics are used. Banks have started using single biometric systems for financial transactions. In order to provide further security for online banking transactions, the proposed system introduces the use of multiple(face and fingerprint) biometrics for online financial transaction where both are required for authentication of log-in- process and one biometric is used for transaction process, thus would help overcome traditional vulnerabilities. Further, this proposed research further explores the matching at the feature level, which of course is a under studied problem. Here in this approach, the feature sets extracted from multiple data sources would be fused to create a new feature set to represent the individual. Since the feature set contains better-off information about the fresh biometric data compared to the match score level or the final decision, combination at this level is possible to provide better authentication results. Initial results indicate that the planned technique can lead to large improvement in multimodal matching performance.

Paper 3: A Secure Web Server for E-Banking

Author: Orvila Sarker, Mehedi Hasan, N. M. Istiak Chowdhury

The main challenge in any online banking system is to secure information that stored in web server, also providing extra degree of privacy to individual bank client during every transaction. Unfortunately, traditional systems do not provide the scope to hide an individual client's transaction information in the server. As a result, there is a chance of being cheated by any bank employee or the authority who are responsible behind running the system. In this work we propose a method to design a secure web server using RC4 algorithm for online banking system. In this system, we have introduced a secure money transaction process by introducing a secrete key during each transaction made by the client or user. Only the valid client or authorized user can able to access his information. For this he has to make a registration to the system by providing some basic information about himself. But it's really important to memorize the encryption key which provides both the encryption & decryption. If a user forgets this key, he will not be able to make any transaction.

Paper 4: One Touch Multi-banking Transaction ATM System using Biometric and GSM Authentication

Authors: Apurva Taralekar, Rutuja Tangade, Gopalsingh Chouhan, Nikhilkumar Shardoor

Every individuals has multiple bank accounts in different banks, people's need to carry multiple ATM cards for transaction, there may be different PINs for every account. In traditional system, ATM terminal customer recognition systems only rely on bank cards, security pin number, and such identity verification methods which measures are not perfect and functions are too single and at times there are incidents where we forget ours security PIN number, lose our cards, cards get stolen, stolen PIN numbers. To overcome the bugs in traditional ATM system, introducing a new ATM terminal customer recognition system, "One touch Multi-banking Transaction system using Biometric and GSM Authentication". Biometric based fingerprint authentication technique is one of the most secure systems, unauthorized accesses are restricted, as this makes fingerprint a unique identification for everyone. This system also assures a secure GSM (OTP-One time Password) based transaction. Here the proposed system has no risk overhead in managing multiple account transactions and achieves high security as compare to the traditional ATM system.

Paper 5: Multilevel Security Feature for Online Transaction using QR Code & Digital Watermarking

Authors: Aayushi Mishra , Manish Mathuria

The utilization of the online services especially the access to Internet Banking services has grown rapidly from last five years. The Internet Banking services provide the customers with the secure and reliable environment to deal with. But with the technology advancement, it is mandatory for the banks to put into practice the ideal technologies or the best security strategies and procedures to authorize or validate the originality of the customers. This must be done to ensure that the data or the information being transmitted during any kind of transaction is safe and no kind of leakage or modification of the information is possible for the intruder. This paper presents a digital watermark method for the QR Code (Quick Response Code) In this, a visible watermark is embedded in the QR Code image using the watermark technology (DCT) and describes the functioning feature of a secure authorization system by means of QR codes & the digital watermark for Internet Banking.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In previous days, they used only single level authentication like OTP generation. It was not more secured. Secure electronic transaction (SET) It involves many levels of encryption, using many combinations of symmetric cryptography, asymmetric cryptography and hashing. It does not assume that each agent has his own private key so that the only problem which is remained is the distribution of the public keys, but allows cardholders to decide their asymmetric key.

3.1.1 Drawbacks

1. User must have credit card
2. It is not cost-effective when the payment is small.
3. Could get out of sync
4. Can lock you out of your account.
5. Cost and complexity for merchants to offer support, contrasted with the comparatively low cost and simplicity of the existing SSL based alternative.
6. Client-side certificate distribution logistics.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

This uses machine learning techniques to get a high degree of accuracy from what is called “training data”. Haar Cascades use the Adaboost learning algorithm which selects a small number of important features from a large set to give an efficient result of classifiers. Initially, the algorithm needs a lot of positive images (images of

faces) and negative images (images without faces) to train the classifier. Then we need to extract features from it. For this, haar features shown in below image are used. They are just like our convolutional kernel. Each feature is a single value obtained by subtracting sum of pixels under white rectangle from sum of pixels under black rectangle.

Face Detection determines the locations and sizes of human faces in arbitrary (digital) images.

In **Face Recognition**, the use of Face Detection comes first to determine and isolate a face before it can be recognized.

3.2.1 Advantages

- The key advantage of a Haar-like feature over most other features is its calculation speed.

- Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video
- Haar Cascades use the Adaboost learning algorithm which selects a small number of important features from a large set to give an efficient result of classifiers.
- Enhanced security.
- Faster processing.
- Seamless integration.
- Automation of identification.
- Breach of privacy.
- Vulnerability in recognition.
- Massive data storage.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the project and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is to be carried out. This is to ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential. Three key considerations involved in the feasibility analysis are

3.3.1. Economic feasibility

3.3.2. Technical feasibility

3.3.3. Social feasibility

3.3.4. Operational feasibility

3.3.1 ECONOMICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the developed system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the technical feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. A feasibility study evaluates the project's potential for success.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. This level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

3.3.4 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

Operational feasibility refers to the measure of solving problems with the help of a new proposed system. It helps in taking advantage of the opportunities and fulfills the requirements as identified during the development of the project. It takes care that the management and the users support the project.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 4.1: System Design

4.2 UML DIAGRAMS

UML stands for Unified Modeling Language. UML is a standardized general-purpose modeling language in the field of object-oriented software engineering. The standard is managed, and was created by, the Object Management Group.

The goal is for UML to become a common language for creating models of object-oriented computer software. In its current form UML is comprised of two major components: a Meta-model and a notation. In the future, some form of method or process may also be added to; or associated with, UML.

The Unified Modeling Language is a standard language for specifying, Visualization, Constructing and documenting the artifacts of software system, as well as for business modeling and other non-software systems.

The UML represents a collection of best engineering practices that have proven successful in the modeling of large and complex systems.

The UML is a very important part of developing objects oriented software and the software development process. The UML uses mostly graphical notations to express the design of software projects.

Goals:

The Primary goals in the design of the UML are as follows:

1. Provide users a ready-to-use, expressive visual modeling Language so that they can develop and exchange meaningful models.
2. Provide extendibility and specialization mechanisms to extend the core concepts.
3. Be independent of particular programming languages and development process.
4. Provide a formal basis for understanding the modeling language.
5. Encourage the growth of OO tools market.

6. Support higher level development concepts such as collaborations, frameworks, patterns and components.
7. Integrate best practices.

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM:

A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

Fig. 4.2: Use case Diagram

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

A sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how processes operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart. Sequence diagrams are sometimes called event diagrams, event scenarios, and timing diagrams.

Fig.4.3: Sequence Diagram

4.2.3 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

Activity diagrams are graphical representations of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams can be used to describe the business and operational step-by-step workflows of components in a system. An activity diagram shows the overall flow of control.

Fig.4.4: Activity Diagram

4.2.4 CLASS DIAGRAM

The purpose of class diagram is to model the static view of an application. Class diagrams are the only diagrams which can be directly mapped with object-oriented languages and thus widely used at the time of construction. Class diagram is a static diagram. It represents the static view of an application. Class diagram is not only used for visualizing, describing, and documenting different aspects of a system but also for constructing executable code of the software application.

Fig.4.5: Class Diagram

4.2.5 DEPLOYMENT DIAGRAM

A deployment diagram is a UML diagram type that shows the execution architecture of a system, including nodes such as hardware or software execution environments, and the middleware connecting them.

Deployment diagrams are typically used to visualize the physical hardware and software of a system. Using it you can understand how the system will be physically deployed on the hardware.

Deployment diagrams help model the hardware topology of a system compared to other UML diagram types which mostly outline the logical components of a system.

Fig.4.6: Deployment Diagram

4.3 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM:

1. The DFD is also called as bubble chart. It is a simple graphical formalism that can be used to represent a system in terms of input data to the system, various processing carried out on this data, and the output data is generated by this system.
2. The data flow diagram (DFD) is one of the most important modeling tools. It is used to model the system components. These components are the system process, the data used by the process, an external entity that interacts with the system and the information flows in the system.
3. DFD shows how the information moves through the system and how it is modified by a series of transformations. It is a graphical technique that depicts information flow and the transformations that are applied as data moves from input to output.
4. DFD is also known as bubble chart. A DFD may be used to represent a system at any level of abstraction. DFD may be partitioned into levels that represent increasing information flow and functional detail.

DFD-0

Fig.4.7 : Level 0

DFD-1

Fig.4.8 : Level 1

DFD-2

Fig.4.9 : Level 2

OVERALL DFD

Fig.4.10 : Overall DFD

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE SPECIFICATION

- ✓ PROCESSOR : PENTIUM IV
- ✓ RAM : 8 GB
- ✓ PROCESSOR : 2.4 GHZ
- ✓ MAIN MEMORY : 8GB RAM
- ✓ PROCESSING SPEED : 600 MHZ
- ✓ HARD DISK DRIVE : 1TB
- ✓ KEYBOARD : 104 KEYS

5.2 SOFTWARE SPECIFICATION

- ✓ FRONT END : PYTHON
- ✓ SQLite
- ✓ IDE : ANACONDA
- ✓ OPERATING SYSTEM : WINDOWS 10

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATIONS

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 PYTHON

Python is an object-oriented programming language created by Guido Rossum in 1989. It is ideally designed for rapid prototyping of complex applications. It has interfaces to many OS system calls and libraries and is extensible to C or C++. Many large companies use the Python programming language include NASA, Google, YouTube, BitTorrent, etc. Python programming is widely used in Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Generation, Neural Networks and other advanced fields of Computer Science. Python had deep focus on code readability & this class will teach you python from basics.

6.1.1.1 FEATURES OF PYTHON

- It provides rich data types and easier to read syntax than any other programming languages
- It is a platform independent scripted language with full access to operating system API's
- Compared to other programming languages, it allows more run-time flexibility
- It includes the basic text manipulation facilities of Perl and Awk
- A module in Python may have one or more classes and free functions
- Libraries in Python's are cross-platform compatible with Linux, Macintosh, and Windows

- For building large applications, Python can be compiled to byte-code
- Python supports functional and structured programming as well as OOP
- It supports interactive mode that allows interacting Testing and debugging of snippets of code
- In Python, since there is no compilation step, editing, debugging and testing is fast.

6.1.1.2 APPLICATIONS OF PYTHON PROGRAMMING

Web Applications

You can create scalable Web Apps using frameworks and CMS (Content Management System) that are built on Python. Some of the popular platforms for creating Web Apps are: Django, Flask, Pyramid, Plone, Django CMS. Sites like Mozilla, Reddit, Instagram and PBS are written in Python.

Scientific and Numeric Computing

There are numerous libraries available in Python for scientific and numeric computing. There are libraries like: SciPy and NumPy that are used in general purpose computing. And, there are specific libraries like: EarthPy for earth science, AstroPy for Astronomy and so on. Also, the language is heavily used in machine learning, data mining and deep learning.

Creating software Prototypes

Python is slow compared to compiled languages like C++ and Java. It might not be a good choice if resources are limited and efficiency is a must. However, Python is a great language for creating prototypes. For example: You can use Pygame

(library for creating games) to create your game's prototype first. If you like the prototype, you can use language like C++ to create the actual game.

Good Language to Teach Programming

Python is used by many companies to teach programming to kids and newbies. It is a good language with a lot of features and capabilities. Yet, it's one of the easiest language to learn because of its simple easy-to-use syntax.

About OpenCV Package

Python is a general purpose programming language started by Guido van Rossum, which became very popular in short time mainly because of its simplicity and code readability. It enables the programmer to express his ideas in fewer lines of code without reducing any readability.

Compared to other languages like C/C++, Python is slower. But another important feature of Python is that it can be easily extended with C/C++. This feature helps us to write computationally intensive codes in C/C++ and create a Python wrapper for it so that we can use these wrappers as Python modules. This gives us two advantages: first, our code is as fast as original C/C++ code (since it is the actual C++ code working in background) and second, it is very easy to code in Python. This is how OpenCV-Python works, it is a Python wrapper around original C++ implementation.

And the support of Numpy makes the task more easier. Numpy is a highly optimized library for numerical operations. It gives a MATLAB-style syntax. All the OpenCV array structures are converted to-and-from Numpy arrays. So whatever operations you can do in Numpy, you can combine it with OpenCV, which increases number of weapons in your arsenal. Besides that, several other

libraries like SciPy, Matplotlib which supports Numpy can be used with this.

So OpenCV-Python is an appropriate tool for fast prototyping of computer vision problems.

DOWNLOADING AND INSTALLATION STEPS FOR INSTALLING ANACONDA ON WINDOWS

Follow the steps below to install the Anaconda distribution of Python on Windows.

Steps:

1. Download the Anaconda installer.

Select Windows

Select Windows where the three operating systems are listed.

Download

Download the most recent Python 3 release. At the time of writing, the most recent release was the Python 3.6 Version. Python 2.7 is legacy Python. For problem solvers, select the Python 3.6 version. If you are unsure if your computer is running a 64-bit or 32-bit version of Windows, select 64-bit as 64-bit Windows is most common.

2. Double click the installer to launch.

Open and run the installer

Once the download completes, open and run the .exe installer

3. Click Next.

At the beginning of the install, you need to click **Next** to confirm the installation.

4. Read the licensing terms and click “I Agree”. Then agree to the license.

5. Select an install for “Just Me” unless you’re installing for all users (which requires Windows Administrator privileges) and click Next.

At the Advanced Installation Options screen, I recommend that you **do not check** "Add Anaconda to my PATH environment variable"

6. After a successful installation you will see the “Thanks for installing Anaconda” dialog box:

If you wish to read more about Anaconda Cloud and how to get started with Anaconda, check the boxes “Learn more about Anaconda Cloud” and “Learn how to get started with Anaconda”. Click the Finish button.

- Orange 3 App
- RStudio

Verifying your installation

You can confirm that Anaconda is installed and working with Anaconda Navigator or conda.

Anaconda Navigator

Anaconda Navigator is a graphical user interface that is automatically installed with Anaconda. Navigator will open if the installation was successful. If Navigator does not open, review our help resources.

Windows: Click Start, search or select Anaconda Navigator from the menu.

macOS: Click Launchpad, select Anaconda Navigator. Or, use Cmd+Space to open Spotlight Search and type “Navigator” to open the program.

Linux: See next section.

Getting started with Navigator

The following applications are available by default in Navigator:

- JupyterLab
- Jupyter Notebook
- Spyder
- VSCode
- Glueviz

6.1.2 SQLite

SQLite is not directly comparable to client/server SQL database engines such as MySQL, Oracle, PostgreSQL, or SQL Server since SQLite is trying to solve a different problem.

Client/server SQL database engines strive to implement a shared repository of enterprise data. They emphasize scalability, concurrency, centralization, and control. SQLite strives to provide local data storage for individual applications and devices. SQLite emphasizes economy, efficiency, reliability, independence, and simplicity

SQLite3 can be integrated with Python using `sqlite3` module, which was written by Gerhard Haring. It provides an SQL interface compliant with the DB-API 2.0 specification described by PEP 249. You do not need to install this module separately because it is shipped by default along with Python version 2.5.x onwards.

To use `sqlite3` module, you must first create a connection object that represents the database and then optionally you can create a cursor object, which will help you in executing all the SQL statements.

Python `sqlite3` module APIs

Following are important `sqlite3` module routines, which can suffice your requirement to work with SQLite database from your Python program. If you are looking for a more sophisticated application, then you can look into Python `sqlite3` module's official documentation.

`sqlite3.connect(database [,timeout ,other optional arguments])`

This API opens a connection to the SQLite database file. You can use ":memory:" to open a database connection to a database that resides in RAM instead of on disk. If database is opened successfully, it returns a connection object.

When a database is accessed by multiple connections, and one of the processes modifies the database, the SQLite database is locked until that transaction is committed. The timeout parameter specifies how long the connection should wait for the lock to go away until raising an exception. The default for the timeout parameter is 5.0 (five seconds).

If the given database name does not exist then this call will create the database. You can specify filename with the required path as well if you want to create a database anywhere else except in the current directory.

connection.cursor([cursorClass])

This routine creates a cursor which will be used throughout of your database programming with Python. This method accepts a single optional parameter cursorClass. If supplied, this must be a custom cursor class that extends sqlite3.

connection.close()

This method closes the database connection. Note that this does not automatically call commit(). If you just close your database connection without calling commit() first, your changes will be lost!

Connect To Database

Following Python code shows how to connect to an existing database. If the database does not exist, then it will be created and finally a database object will be

returned.

```
#!/usr/bin/python
```

```
import sqlite3
```

```
conn = sqlite3.connect('test.db')
```

```
print "Opened database successfully";
```

Here, you can also supply database name as the special name :memory: to create a database in RAM. Now, let's run the above program to create our database test.db in the current directory. You can change your path as per your requirement. Keep the above code in sqlite.py file and execute it as shown below. If the database is successfully created, then it will display the following message.

```
$chmod +x sqlite.py
```

```
$/sqlite.py
```

```
Open database successfully
```

6.2LIST OF MODULES

6.2.1. Registration

6.2.2. Face Detection

6.2.3. Face Recognition

6.2.4. Pin Generation

6.2.5. Transaction

6.2.1 Registration Module

In this module new user should register their face to get account number. For that they need to fill their personal details like Username, Password and Mail ID.

6.2.2 Face Detection

Face detection is a great tool that can be used in different fields such as security and human resources. OpenCV provides the Haar Feature-based Cascade Classifiers for face detection. This method apply series of classifiers to every subwindow of input picture, the first one classifier eliminates a large number of non-faces examples with very little processing. The other classifiers eliminate additional negatives but require additional computation. After several stages of processing the number of sub-windows have been reduced radically. Filters are used to extract features from image, and those filters became more and more complex in each stage from one to n.

6.2.3 Face Recognition

Facial recognition is a way of recognizing a human face through technology. A facial recognition system uses facial features from a photograph or video. It compares the information with a dataset of known faces to find a match.

Steps Involved

1. A picture of your face is captured from a photo or video. Your face might

appear alone or in a crowd. Your image may show you looking straight ahead or nearly in profile.

2. Facial recognition software reads the geometry of your face. Key factors include the distance between your eyes and the distance from forehead to chin.

3. Your facial signature — a mathematical formula — is compared to a dataset of known faces.

4. A determination is made. Your face print may match that of an image in a facial recognition system dataset.

6.2.4 Pin Generation

In this module pin will be generated face security purpose. Initially we will set our pin we can transact amount through pin or face. If the pin matches transaction will be done. Still, pin generation via E-mail is made instantaneously once when the authorized face is recognized to proceed with the transaction process.

6.2.5 Transaction Module

In this module transaction will be done where user need to enter their details like From account, To account, Amount then face recognition will be done if the face matched and generated pin is entered when it will be authorized user or transaction will not be done.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 GENERAL

In a generalized way, we can say that the system testing is a type of testing in which the main aim is to make sure that system performs efficiently and seamlessly. The process of testing is applied to a program with the main aim to discover an unprecedented error, an error which otherwise could have damaged the future of the software. Test cases which brings up a high possibility of discovering and error is considered successful. This successful test helps to answer the still unknown errors.

TESTING

Testing, as already explained earlier, is the process of discovering all possible weak-points in the finalized software product. Testing helps to counter the working of sub-assemblies, components, assembly and the complete result. The software is taken through different exercises with the main aim of making sure that software meets the business requirement and user-expectations and doesn't fails abruptly. Several types of tests are used today. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

7.2 TYPES OF TESTING

A test plan is a document which describes approach, its scope, its resources and the schedule of aimed testing exercises. It helps to identify almost other test item, the features which are to be tested, its tasks, how will everyone do each task, how much the tester is independent, the environment in which the test is taking place,

its technique of design plus the both the end criteria which is used, also rational of choice of theirs, and whatever kind of risk which requires emergency planning. It can be also referred to as the record of the process of test planning. Test plans are usually prepared with signification input from test engineers.

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

In unit testing, the design of the test cases is involved that helps in the validation of the internal program logic. The validation of all the decision branches and internal code takes place. After the individual unit is completed it takes place. Plus it is taken into account after the individual unit is completed before integration. The unit test thus performs the basic level test at its component stage and test the particular business process, system configurations etc. The unit test ensures that the particular unique path of the process gets performed precisely to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs with the results which are expected.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

These tests are designed to test the integrated software items to determine whether if they really execute as a single program or application. The testing is event driven and thus is concerned with the basic outcome of field. The Integration tests demonstrate that the components were individually satisfaction, as already represented by successful unit testing, the components are apt and fine. This type of testing is specially aimed to expose the issues that come-up by the components combination.

7.2.3 PERFORMANCE TESTING

It determines the amount of execution time spent in various parts of the unit, program throughput and response time and device utilization by the program unit.

7.2.4 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

The functional tests help in providing the systematic representation that functions tested are available and specified by technical requirement, documentation of the system and the user manual.

7.2.5 SYSTEM TESTING

System testing, as the name suggests, is the type of testing in which ensure that the software system meet the business requirements and aim. Testing of the configuration is taken place here to ensure predictable result and thus analysis of it. System testing is relied on the description of process and its flow, stressing on pre driven process and the points of integration.

7.2.6 WHITE BOX TESTING

The white box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the system software is open and can be processed by the tester. It is therefore a complex type of testing process. All the data structure, components etc. are tested by the tester himself to find out a possible bug or error. It is used in situation in which the black box is incapable of finding out a bug. It is a complex type of testing which takes more time to get applied.

7.2.7 BLACK BOX TESTING

The black box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the

software is hidden and only the input and output of the system is the key for the tester to find out a bug. It is therefore a simple type of testing. A programmer with basic knowledge can also process this type of testing. It is less time consuming as compared to the white box testing. It is very successful for software which are less complex are straight-forward in nature. It is also less costly than white box testing.

7.2.8 ACCEPTANCE TESTING

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the existing system, the bank transaction methods involved only single level authentication like one-time password generation, which was not much secure.

Then introduced the concept called SET-Secure Electronic Transaction which includes symmetric cryptography, asymmetric cryptography and hashing techniques. Here the cardholders or the users can decide their own asymmetric key that is to have their own private key but the problem remained is the public key distribution.

Whereas in the traditional systems, there is a lack of security due to intruders and other hacking process involved like spoofing, Middle-in-the-Man attack, phishing attacks, etc.

The proposed system uses the technique of machine learning to attain the high degree of accuracy on training data. Face detection and face recognition are the most important modules to be processed for the secure transaction purpose.

In this study, we introduced a facial recognition system to provide a secured and reliable bank transaction. The introduction of the deep for facial authentication had proven to be effective in maximizing security level when performing banking transactions. It is expected that the security level of mobile banking to increase with the employment networks for face authentication.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Conclusion

Realized a reliable, real-time face recognition system on machine learning. According to the new technical era, some advancement has taken place and some techniques of facial recognition have achieved popularity. We are using Haar cascade algorithm for face recognition. Capture module deals with the configuration of video interface and performs the real-time video capture. Face Detection module analyses each captured frame and extracts valid faces from each frame. Face Identification deals with face recognition and verification of the detected face.

Future Work

Though the proposed system has high degree of accuracy and security at each modules of face recognition and pin generation, still there exists the drawback which has to be reduced by using enhancement techniques.

The existence of fake user is possible in the proposed system due to registration made by unauthorized users for fraudulent access.

In Future any fraudulent access by the fake user is eliminated with the help of radio frequency identification card.

APPENDICES

A. CODING

```
import cv2, sys, numpy, os

haar_file =
'F:\github\opencv-master\data\haarcascades\haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml'

# All the faces data will be
# present this folder
datasets = 'datasets'

# These are sub data sets of folder,
# for my faces I've used my name you can
# change the label here
sub_data = 'saran'
path = os.path.join(datasets, sub_data)
if not os.path.isdir(path):
    os.mkdir(path)

# defining the size of images
(width, height) = (130, 100)

# '0' is used for my webcam,
# if you've any other camera
# attached use '1' like this
```

```

face_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier(haar_file)
webcam = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
# The program loops until it has 30 images of the face.
count = 1
while count < 30:
    (_, im) = webcam.read()
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(im, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    faces = face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.3, 4)
    for (x, y, w, h) in faces:
        cv2.rectangle(im, (x, y), (x + w, y + h), (255, 0, 0), 2)
        face = gray[y:y + h, x:x + w]
        face_resize = cv2.resize(face, (width, height))
        cv2.imwrite('% s/% s.png' % (path, count), face_resize)
    count += 1
    cv2.imshow('OpenCV', im)
    key = cv2.waitKey(10)
    if key == 27:
        break
webcam.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows()

import cv2, sys, numpy, os
size = 4
haar_file =
'F:\github\opencv-master\data\haarcascades\haarcascade_frontalface_default.xml'
datasets = 'datasets'

```

```

# Part 1: Create fisherRecognizer
print('Recognizing Face Please Be in sufficient Lights...')

# Create a list of images and a list of corresponding names
(images, lables, names, id) = ([], [], {}, 0)
for (subdirs, dirs, files) in os.walk(datasets):
    for subdir in dirs:
        names[id] = subdir
        subjectpath = os.path.join(datasets, subdir)
        for filename in os.listdir(subjectpath):
            path = subjectpath + '/' + filename
            lable = id
            images.append(cv2.imread(path, 0))
            lables.append(int(lable))
        id += 1
(width, height) = (130, 100)

# Create a Numpy array from the two lists above
(images, lables) = [numpy.array(lis) for lis in [images, lables]]

# OpenCV trains a model from the images
# NOTE FOR OpenCV2: remove '.face'
model = cv2.face.LBPHFaceRecognizer_create()
model.train(images, lables)

# Part 2: Use fisherRecognizer on camera stream

```

```

face_cascade = cv2.CascadeClassifier(haar_file)
webcam = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
while True:
    (_, im) = webcam.read()
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(im, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
    faces = face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray, 1.3, 5)
    for (x, y, w, h) in faces:
        cv2.rectangle(im, (x, y), (x + w, y + h), (255, 0, 0), 2)
        face = gray[y:y + h, x:x + w]
        face_resize = cv2.resize(face, (width, height))
        # Try to recognize the face
        prediction = model.predict(face_resize)
        cv2.rectangle(im, (x, y), (x + w, y + h), (0, 255, 0), 3)
        if prediction[1]<500:
            cv2.putText(im, '% s - %.0f' %
(names[prediction[0]], prediction[1]), (x-10, y-10),
cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_PLAIN, 1, (0, 255, 0))
        else:
            cv2.putText(im, 'not recognized',
(x-10, y-10), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_PLAIN, 1, (0, 255, 0))
        cv2.imshow('OpenCV', im)
        key = cv2.waitKey(10)
        if key == 27:
            break
webcam.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows()

```

B. SCREENSHOTS

Registration

Face Recognition

Email Acknowledgement

(no subject) Inbox x

hospitalpatientinfosys2020@gmail.com

to ▾

9760174343040469

 Reply

 Forward

Face Detection

Pin Generation

(no subject) Inbox x

hospitalpatientinfosys2020@gmail.com

to ▾

8979

 Reply

 Forward

Transaction

```
Enter user name: mani
Enter email: monicaasreemanju@gmail.com
Enter account No: 9760174343040469
('mani', '1999', 'monicaasreemanju@gmail.com', '9876543210', '9760174343040469', '1000')
would you like to transact the money: y
From account no: 9760174343040469
To account no: 9760174343040463
receipient name: manju
Amount: 100
Would you like to proceed with authentication via (face ): face
Recognizing Face Please Be in sufficient Lights...
Enter PIN: 8979
transaction done!

your current Balance: ('900',)
```

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